

LOGIC AGGREGATION BY QUANTIFIER ‘MOST OF’ FOR ENTITIES EVALUATION

MIROSLAV HUDEC^{1,2}, FRANTIŠEK PAPALA³, HANNA KRISTÍN SKAFTADÓTTIR⁴

¹ University of Economics in Bratislava, Faculty of Economic Informatics, Bratislava, Slovakia, miroslav.hudec@euba.sk 0000-0002-2868-0322

² VSB – Technical University of Ostrava, Faculty of Economics, Ostrava, Czech Republic, miroslav.hudec@vsb.cz,

³ VSB – Technical University of Ostrava, Faculty of Economics, Ostrava, Czech Republic, frantisek.papala.st@vsb.cz, 0009-0009-8384-5474

⁴ Bifröst University, Department of Business, Bifröst, Iceland, hannak@bifrost.is, 0000-0001-5228-8294

Abstract: People often consider that when a number of satisfied elementary requirements increases, the entity should be more relevant. For this case, we need mixed aggregation function covering cases from nilpotent conjunction to nilpotent disjunction. In these cases, the aggregation of elementary requirements is formalised by the quantifier “most of” or variants thereof. However, this aggregation does not support mandatory or optional elementary requirements. Thus, we also explored how to aggregate mandatory and optional requirements with quantified aggregation. Next, we discussed how to augment business intelligence reporting by quantified aggregation and raised future research topics in assigning weights and recognising dependencies between elementary requirements.

Keywords: Fuzzy relative quantifier, Mixed aggregation function, Mandatory requirements, Business intelligence reporting.

1. INTRODUCTION

In a business environment (or in everyday evaluation), people often consider that when a number of satisfied elementary requirements increases, the entity (product, customer, holiday destination) should be more relevant. On the contrary, when a number of satisfied elementary conditions decreases, the entity should be downplayed.

In this case, people evaluate somewhere between conjunctive aggregation (all elementary conditions should be satisfied) and disjunctive aggregation (at least one elementary condition should be satisfied). The former is restrictive, that is, an entity is rejected even though only one elementary condition is not met. This might lead to the empty answer problem (Bosc et al., 2008). The latter aggregation might be considered as too relaxed, that is, an entity is suitable if it meets at least one elementary condition, which leads to the overabundant answer problem (Bosc et al., 2008).

The main classification of aggregation functions applied in logical evaluation is due to (Dubois and Prade, 2004): conjunctive, averaging, disjunctive, and mixed. Generally, we can express conjunctive functions as $0 \leq A(\mathbf{x}) \leq \min(\mathbf{x})$, averaging functions as $\min(\mathbf{x}) \leq A(\mathbf{x}) \leq \max(\mathbf{x})$, disjunctive functions as $\max(\mathbf{x}) \leq A(\mathbf{x}) \leq 1$, and mixed aggregation functions (which can be adapted to data, that is, behave in different parts of domains differently), where \mathbf{x} is a vector of elementary satisfaction degrees $\mathbf{x} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$.

Although the functions *min* and *max* might be considered too restrictive or too relaxed, respectively, the other conjunctive functions are even more restrictive (downward reinforcement), while the other disjunctive functions are even more relaxed (upward reinforcement) (Grabisch et al., 2009).

We can easily imagine a situation where two out of ten elementary satisfied conditions are not a good evaluation, while eight out of ten elementary satisfied conditions are a good evaluation. When about half atomic conditions are met, there is space for averaging evaluation (more or less good entity). Therefore, we need a mixed aggregation function. The question is which one and, moreover, how to adjust its parameters. But also considering its intuitiveness for the domain expert.

Elementary conditions can be partially satisfied or satisfied to some degree. For instance, a good sell results might be expressed as less than 1 000 definitely not good, more than 1 500 definitely good, while between 1 000 and 1 500 partially good, where satisfaction increases as we approach value 1 500.

Even binary data might exhibit intensities of satisfaction. For example, a hotel room has a balcony or does not have one. But the customer might interpret the requirement as: *it is irrelevant to me, I prefer the balcony, I weakly prefer the balcony, I strongly prefer balcony, or the balcony must be*. This option is handled by the proximity relation (Hudec et al., 2024).

In this work, to cover the observations mentioned above, we focus on mixed aggregation functions formalized by a quantifier *most of*.

After this introduction the article continues with theoretical observations and examples in Section 2, while Section 3 is devoted to aggregation of mandatory and optional requirements into the quantified aggregation. Section 4 is focused on discussion and business intelligence reporting. Finally, Section 5 concludes this work.

2. THEORETICAL OBSERVATIONS

Mixed aggregation functions are not always intuitive to users, or are complex. Further, they might be non-associative (like ordinal sums (Hudec et al., 2021)), non-continuous in borderline cases (like uninorms (Munar et al., 2023)), cover only specific functions (gamma operator (Dujmović, 2018)), and the like. All of them have shown benefits in a variety of tasks. But for searching the best entities, rewarding according to intensities of satisfying majority of requirements, or in business intelligence reporting is too complex.

In this work, we evaluate the aggregation by a relative quantifier *most of* and its variants to meet the basic properties of the aggregation functions (Grabisch et al., 2009) borderline cases $f(0, 0, \dots, 0) = 0$ and $f(1, 1, \dots, 1) = 1$, and monotonicity.

Data evaluation and classification are mental processes of reasoning and, therefore, belong to logic (Dujmović, 2018). In these tasks, we should cover the following reasoning requirements:

- Downplay relevance of low elementary scores (conjunctive reinforcement: strict or nilpotent), the solution is lower than or equal to (equal stands for case where we observe clear non-satisfaction of at least one elementary condition) the minimal degree of all elementary conditions.
- Emphasizing the relevance of high scores (disjunctive reinforcement: strict or nilpotent), the solution is higher than or equal to (equal stands for case where we observe full satisfaction of at least one elementary condition) maximal degree of all elementary conditions.
- Neutrality, when the decrease in the value of one (or more) elementary requirements is fully compensated by the same increase in the value of another (one or more) elementary requirement.
- Pessimistic inclination, when elementary requirements should be simultaneously (at least partially) satisfied, but the result is lower than the neutrality and higher than the minimal value.
- Optimistic inclination (or the levels of substitutability) when elementary conditions should be satisfied, but the result is higher than neutrality and lower than maximal value.

Quantified aggregation has been introduced in (Kacprzyk and Ziółkowski, 1986) for relaxing relational database SQL queries managed by AND connective. Recent work (Sojka et al., 2020) has shown that the same basic structure of linguistic summaries proposed by Yager (1982) and quantified aggregation are modifications of one function, either for summarization or quantified aggregation.

The quantified linguistic summarization is formalized as follows:

$$v(\mathbf{x}) = \mu_Q(p) \tag{1}$$

where \mathbf{x} is the vector of the values of the considered attributes of an entity and

$$p = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_{P_i}(\mathbf{x}) \tag{2}$$

is the proportion of entities that meet (fully or partially) the set of elementary conditions P_i , where n is the number of elementary conditions posed on a subset of attributes and μ_P and μ_Q are membership functions that express the intensity of belonging to the elementary condition and quantifier, respectively.

Next, we need to formalise quantifier *most of*, or variants thereof (Kacprzyk and Zadrożny, 2009, Zadeh, 1983). Quantifier can be formalized as a monotone or strict monotone function. In the latter, we cover data evaluation, i.e., only entity which fully meets all elementary conditions gets degree of 1. In the former, we are able to classify into rejected entities, partially accepted entities and fully accepted entities, because the function has an interval of rejection and full acceptance. The monotone function is depicted in Figure 1, where $m < n \leq 1$.

Usually, $m = 0.5$, to express that majority means more than half. When $n < 1$, we get three zones shown in Figure 1: A - nilpotent conjunction - entities are rejected or behaviour is below threshold, B - averaging or smooth transition from rejection to acceptance, and C - nilpotent disjunction - entities are accepted or behaviour is excellent.

Quantifiers are deeply discussed in e.g., (Murinová and Novák, 2024). For aggregation, only quantifiers expressed as monotone increasing or strictly increasing are suitable to meet the main properties of aggregation functions.

Figure 1: Quantifier *most of* as a monotone function

We propose a fuzzy aggregation mechanism based on relative quantifier *most of* as an aggregation function that produces a single holistic satisfaction score – essentially a tunable relaxation of conjunction and intensification of disjunction. This function balances between conjunctive (“all”) and disjunctive (“at least one”) logic in a continuous manner.

2.1 Illustrative example

Let us have ten elementary conditions P_1, P_2, \dots, P_{10} and a set of ten entities e_1, e_2, \dots, e_{10} to illustrate all the above-mentioned reasoning requirements. Parameters m and n (Figure 1) get values 0.5 and 0.85, respectively. The solution is in Table 1. For instance, entities are products, while conditions are preferred properties.

Table 1: Satisfaction degrees of elementary conditions and solutions by quantified aggregation, arithmetic mean, min and max functions

Entity	P ₁	P ₂	P ₃	P ₄	P ₅	P ₆	P ₇	P ₈	P ₉	P ₁₀	solution (2)	arithm. mean	min	max
e ₁	1	0.8	0.9	0.2	0	0.9	0.4	0.85	0.9	0.6	0.443	0.655	0	1
e ₂	1	0	1	1	1	0.75	0.8	0.9	0.6	0.9	0.843	0.795	0	1
e ₃	0.75	0.85	0.9	0.85	0.95	0.7	0	1	0.9	0.85	0.786	0.775	0	1
e ₄	1	0.9	0.2	0.3	0	0.15	0.85	0.35	0.7	1	0.129	0.545	0	1
e ₅	0.8	0.9	0.95	0.85	0.8	0.85	0.95	0.9	0.9	0.8	1	0.87	0.8	0.95
e ₆	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.35	0.11	0.22	0.1	0.4	0.2	0.35	0	0.253	0.1	0.4
e ₇	0	0.8	0.95	0.75	0.9	0.45	1	0.55	0	0.65	0.3	0.605	0	1
e ₈	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
e ₉	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
e ₁₀	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0	0.5	0.5	0.5

By observing entities e_8 and e_9 we see that the borderline cases are met. Entity e_{10} has idempotent behavior for all functions except quantified aggregation. It is expected because 0.5 is not majority of and, therefore, we have a nilpotent conjunction. Monotonicity is a matter of direct observation. Entities e_5 and e_6 exhibit a nilpotent disjunction (full acceptance) and a nilpotent conjunction (full rejection). When the proportion is closer to 0.5, than to 0.85 we have pessimistic inclination for entity e_1 , while for entity e_2 we have optimistic inclination, as the proportion is approaching 0.85. Entities e_3 and e_4 indicate these inclinations and support the observation of monotonicity.

This function smoothly covers downplay, pessimistic inclination, through neutrality to optimistic inclination and to emphasizing entities. In this way, we covered the required aspects of mixed aggregation functions with a simple and easily applicable function.

2.2 Limitations

We should note that this aggregation (similarly as the arithmetic mean) does not cover the mandatory conditions or optional (full) alternatives.

3. QUANTIFIED AGGREGATION AGGREGATED WITH MANDATORY OR OPTIONAL CONDITIONS

This section focusses on aggregation when evaluation contains mandatory condition(s) and for the other holds *to more to merrier*, or optional full alternative(s) and for the other holds *to more to merrier*.

3.1 Mandatory conditions

In cost-benefit conditions, we have mandatory requirements like price. For example, when rewarding workers, they should meet the key requirement, and the other might be considered as if more of them satisfied it is better. The next example is accommodation: price should be met, while the majority of other requirements like distance to city center, breakfast quality and the like should be met. We formalize it in the following way:

$$v(\mathbf{x}) = \bigwedge_{i=1}^l P_i \wedge \mu_Q(p) \quad (3)$$

where l is the number of mandatory requirements, while the proportion p is expressed as:

$$p = \frac{1}{n-l} \sum_{j=n-l}^n \mu_{P_j}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (4)$$

the other variables have the same meaning as in (1) and (2). Naturally, the question of the suitable conjunction appears. Quantified part is relaxed in comparison to conjunction. Hence, when we want to make aggregation stricter, options for conjunction are Łukasiewicz t-norm ($t(x_1, x_2) = \max(0, x_1 + x_2 - 1)$) or product t-norm ($t(x_1, x_2) = x_1 x_2$).

The initial example (Table 1) is modified that P_1 is mandatory requirement, while all the other requirements holds requirement *to more to merrier*.

Table 2: Satisfaction degrees of elementary conditions and solutions by conjunction of mandatory requirement and quantified aggregation of the other requirements

Entity	P ₁	P ₂	P ₃	P ₄	P ₅	P ₆	P ₇	P ₈	P ₉	P ₁₀	solution (3) by Łuk.t-norm
e ₁	1	0.8	0.9	0.2	0	0.9	0.4	0.85	0.9	0.6	0.333
e ₂	1	0	1	1	1	0.75	0.8	0.9	0.6	0.9	0.778
e ₃	0.75	0.85	0.9	0.85	0.95	0.7	0	1	0.9	0.85	0.544
e ₄	1	0.9	0.2	0.3	0	0.15	0.85	0.35	0.7	1	0
e ₅	0.8	0.9	0.95	0.85	0.8	0.85	0.95	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.800
e ₆	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.35	0.11	0.22	0.1	0.4	0.2	0.35	0
e ₇	0	0.8	0.95	0.75	0.9	0.45	1	0.55	0	0.65	0
e ₈	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
e ₉	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
e ₁₀	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0

Maintaining the original requirements and modifying the P_1 condition to a mandatory one reveals that certain results remain the same. For instance, the borderline cases in the case of entities e_8 and e_9 are still satisfied. Additionally, entity e_{10} continues to hold a value of zero. When using a conjunction, such as Łukasiewicz's, in a given setting, there can be no increase in satisfaction degrees, only deterioration. This is evidenced by the remaining entities, e_1 to e_7 (except for no change in e_6). Anyway, the monotonicity holds, so this function meets properties of aggregation functions. To reach the value of 1, it is necessary to satisfy

the mandatory condition (P_l) to the maximum value (1) and, concurrently, achieve nilpotent disjunction with the other conditions. This occurs when the proportion is greater than 0.85.

3.2 Optional conditions

Similarly, adding optional requirements into quantified aggregation is not a difficult task. They should be connected by disjunction with the quantified aggregation, i.e., in (3) we replace \wedge with \vee .

We formalize it in the following way:

$$v(x) = \bigvee_{i=1}^l P_i \vee \mu_Q(p) \quad (5)$$

where l is the number of optional requirements, while the proportion p is expressed as:

$$p = \frac{1}{n-l} \sum_{j=n-l}^n \mu_{P_j}(x) \quad (6)$$

the other variables have the same meaning as in (1) and (2). Analogously, the question of the suitable disjunction appears. Quantified part is intensified in comparison to disjunction. Hence, when we want to make aggregation weaker and therefore options for disjunction are Łukasiewicz t-conorm ($t(x_1, x_2) = \min(1, x_1 + x_2)$) or probabilistic sum t-conorm ($t(x_1, x_2) = x_1 + x_2 - x_1 x_2$).

4. DISCUSSION AND BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE REFLECTION

The proposed fuzzy-majority aggregation is scalable to any number of elementary requirements and entities; however, high intercorrelation among elementary requirements may distort the score. When many criteria are strongly dependent, a preliminary correlation (or collinearity) test is advisable before aggregating the data.

Another open issue is the assignment of weights. While averaging operators naturally incorporate weights that sum to 1, defining weights for conjunctive or disjunctive components is a more involved process. In conjunctive aggregation all conditions are very relevant, because they are mandatory. One promising avenue is to encode importance through fuzzy implications (Zadrozny et al., 2008), a topic we leave for future work.

Overall, the fuzzy-majority approach mirrors human reasoning by down-valuing alternatives that meet only a few criteria and up-valuing those that satisfy the majority. It offers a flexible yet rigorous tool that extends the querying in business intelligence.

Business intelligence queries often involve multiple criteria that managers or decision-makers consider simultaneously. The same empty-answer or over-abundance described in Sections 1–2 occurs routinely in business intelligence dashboards, where analysts filter entities by multiple key performance indicators (KPIs). For example, a sales manager might seek products that excel across majority of performance metrics (e.g., year-over-year sales growth, profit margin, customer satisfaction, and the like). Using a classical filtering approach with a conjunction could be too rigid, potentially returning no results if no product meets all criteria. By contrast, a fuzzy quantified aggregation that uses the *most of* quantifier can retrieve items that satisfy most of the conditions. For example, one could issue a query like *select products where most of (sales growth > 5%, profit margin > 10%, satisfaction > 80%, etc)* to rank products by how many criteria they fulfill, when the product reaches threshold m (Figure 1). In addition, sales manager is not forced to assign precise values, that is, instead of *sales growth > 5%*, manager might say *sales growth around 5% and more* ensuring that 4.9% is still acceptable, but with a lower degree. This yields a ranked list of products satisfying the majority of criteria. Entities are ranked by intensities of satisfying quantified condition, so usual functions like HEAD showing several the best performing entities can be applied. In effect, fuzzy quantified queries retrieve significant results that conjunctive filters might overlook, while still filtering out largely irrelevant items.

5. CONCLUSION

We face the problems of diverse needs for the logic aggregation of elementary requirements for the evaluation of entities. In this work, we explored quantified aggregation “to more to merrier” that supports the natural way of human evaluation in a smooth transition from nilpotent conjunction across pessimistic and optimistic averaging evaluation to nilpotent disjunction by a simple function. However, this aggregation does not support mandatory or optional requirements. To solve this limitation, we proposed aggregation of mandatory requirements by conjunctive function to quantified aggregation, as well as aggregation of optional

requirements by disjunctive function to quantified aggregation. One of benefits is augmenting business intelligence dashboards with this functionality for example, to rank top entities by quantified aggregation.

The limitation is a possible correlation among elementary requirements, which might skew the result. Thus, the future research topic is recognizing correlation as well as direction of influence to exclude highly correlated and at the same time dependent attributes appearing in elementary conditions.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This article has been produced with the support of the the SGS project no. SP2025/081 of the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic.

LITERATURE

- Bosc, P., Hadjali, A., & Pivert, O. (2008). Empty versus overabundant answers to flexible relational queries. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, 159, 1450–1467.
- Dubois, D., & Prade, H. (2004). On the use of aggregation operations in information fusion processes, *Fuzzy Sets and Systems* 142(1), 143–161.
- Dujmović J. (2018). *Soft Computing Evaluation Logic: the LSP Decision Method and Its Applications*. Hoboken: Wiley–IEEE Computer Society.
- Grabisch M., Marichal J.-L., Mesiar R., & Pap E. (2009). *Aggregation functions*. Cambridge: University Press.
- Hudec, M., Vučetić, M., & Barčáková, N. (2014). *An extended proximity relation and quantified aggregation for designing robust fuzzy query engine*. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 290, 111574.
- Hudec M., Mináriková E., Mesiar R., Saranti A., & Holzinger A. (2021). Classification by ordinal sums of conjunctive and disjunctive functions for explainable AI and interpretable machine learning solutions. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 220, 106916.
- Kacprzyk, J., & Zadrozny, S. (2009). Protoforms of Linguistic Database Summaries as a Human Consistent Tool for Using Natural Language in Data Mining. *International Journal of Software Science and Computational Intelligence*, 1, 1-11.
- Kacprzyk, J. & Ziólkowski, A. (1986). Database queries with fuzzy linguistic quantifiers. *IEEE transactions on systems, man, and cybernetics*, 2007, 16(3), 474-479.
- Munar, M., Hudec, M., Massanet, S., Mináriková, E., & Ruiz-Aguilera, D. (2023). On an Edge Detector Based on Ordinal Sums of Conjunctive and Disjunctive Aggregation Functions. In: S. Massanet, S. Montes, D. Ruiz-Aguilera, & M. González-Hidalgo (Eds). *Fuzzy Logic and Technology, and Aggregation Operators, EUSFLAT AGOP 2023: Vol. 14069. Lecture Notes in Computer Science* (pp. 271-282) Springer.
- Murinová, P., & Novák, V. (2024). Logical syllogisms with “Almost all, Most, Many, A few” and “Several”. *International Journal of Approximate Reasoning*, 175, 109284.
- Sojka P., Hudec M., & Švaňa M. (2020). Linguistic summaries in evaluating elementary conditions, summarizing data and managing nested queries. *Informatica*, 31(4), 841-856.
- Yager, R.R. (1982). A new approach to the summarization of data. *Information Sciences*, 28, 69-86.
- Zadeh, L. A. (1983). A computational approach to fuzzy quantifiers in natural languages. *Computers & Mathematics with Applications*, 9(1), 149–184.
- Zadrozny, S., De Tré, G., De Caluwe, R., & Kacprzyk, J. (2008). An overview of fuzzy approaches to flexible database querying. In J. Galindo (Ed), *Handbook of Research on Fuzzy Information Processing in Databases* (pp. 34-54). Hershey: Information Science Reference.